

Floods and financial stability: Scenario-based evidence from below sea level^{☆,☆☆}

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ARTICLE INFO

JEL classification:

G21
Q54
R30

Keywords:

Floods
Financial stability
Real estate
Credit risk
Climate protection gaps

ABSTRACT

We study whether floods can affect financial stability through a credit risk channel. Our focus is on The Netherlands, a country situated partly below sea level, where insurance policies exclude property damages caused by certain types of floods. Using detailed data for close to EUR 650 billion in real estate exposures, we consider possible implications of uninsurable flood damages for bank capital. For a set of 38 adverse scenarios, we estimate that flood-related property damages lead to capital declines that mostly range between 30 and 50 basis points. We highlight how starting-point loan-to-value ratios are one important indicator of possible capital impacts. Our estimates focus on property damages as the main transmission channel and are also subject to a number of assumptions, suggesting overall effects of flood events may well be larger. If climate protection gaps indeed keep widening across the globe, our analytical approach to quantifying the effects of flood events will become increasingly relevant for financial stability in other jurisdictions.

1. Introduction

Floods can have severe and tragic socio-economic consequences. Examples include the devastating floods after hurricane Katrina in 2005, the 2021 summer floods in Europe, the 2022 floods in Pakistan, and the 2024 floods in both Central Europe and Spain. So far, however, it seems floods have not had major effects on the stability of the financial system. That is to say, flood-related disruptions have not impaired the financial system's ability to serve the real economy. This may change if climate change continues, as it would imply an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events (Auffhammer, 2018). A string of flood events and the associated macroeconomic disruptions may well start affecting financial institutions.

To study floods and financial stability, we focus on the Netherlands, a country that is situated partly below sea level, but where almost

all insurance policies would exclude covering property damages from major floods.¹ Such a climate protection gap may become increasingly relevant to other countries. Swiss Re has indicated that in 2023 only 38% of global economic losses from natural catastrophes were insured. In light of climate change, the impact of natural catastrophes was expected to grow.² For Europe, the ECB and EIOPA (2024) have indicated that insurance protection gaps are expected to widen due to increasing risks related to climate change. For the U.S., Keys and Mulder (2024) find that premia for homeowner insurance have risen sharply in recent years. They project that by 2053, individual households may face a USD 700 increase in their annual premium due to growing disaster risk. Moreover, Sastry et al. (2023) show that in the state of Florida traditional insurers are exiting high risk areas. Recently, the Financial Stability Board (2025) has emphasized how such changes in the

[☆] This article is part of a Special issue entitled: 'CCClimate' published in Journal of Financial Stability.

^{☆☆} With thanks to Wouter Botzen, Karin de Bruijn, Maurice Bun, Ricardo Correa, Hans Degryse, Mattia Girotti, Luc Laeven, Marco Hoogvliet, Hans de Moel, Remco van der Molen, Irene Monasterolo, Klaas Mulier, David Rijsbergen, Stephan Rikkert, Kymo Slager, Robert Vermeulen, Jon Frost, JFS associate editors, and two anonymous reviewers for constructive feedback over the course of this project. We also thank participants at an IMF/ECB workshop, a DNB seminar, online meetings of the International Banking Research Network, and the 2024 Belgian Financial Research Forum for useful comments. Van Ginkel acknowledges financial support under the Horizon Europe ACCREU project, grant agreement No. 101081358. Any errors and omissions remain our own responsibility. Views expressed in this paper do not necessarily coincide with those of de Vrije Universiteit, Deltares, the European Commission, de Nederlandsche Bank or the Eurosystem.

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¹ The online appendix has further details on flood types relevant to the Netherlands. See also Slager (2019).

² Source: <https://www.swissre.com/risk-knowledge/mitigating-climate-risk/natcat-protection-gap-infographic.html#/>. URL last accessed on 14 June 2025.

availability of insurance means that risks are shifted to households, businesses or governments. If climate protection gaps indeed keep widening across the globe, our analytical approach to quantifying the effects of flood events will become increasingly relevant for financial stability in other jurisdictions.

In the event of a flood in the Netherlands, one consequence of uninsured property damages is that lenders need to account for increased credit risk, in particular related to their real estate exposures. We focus on real estate exposures, as these constitute a large share (roughly 45%) of Dutch banks' total assets. In addition, an institutional feature is that Dutch banks can grant relatively large loan amounts to borrowers, namely up to 100% of the collateral. Also, nearly 50% of the mortgage portfolio of Dutch banks consist of interest-only mortgages. Such mortgages imply high exposure amounts as these loans do not amortize until maturity. This combination of large real estate exposures, uninsurable property damages, loans with high loan-to-value (LTV) ratios, and the inherent geographical vulnerability of the country to floods motivates our focus on banks' credit risk. At the same time, we also note that the country has high standards for flood protection, which acts as a crucial mitigant of overall risks—we will return to this point when discussing our results in Section 7.

If and how climate change can affect financial stability remains a topic of debate. In a seminal speech, [Carney \(2015\)](#) argued that climate change can affect financial stability through various channels. One of these channels is physical risk, e.g. property damage and trade disruption due to floods and storms. Likewise, the [European Systemic Risk Board \(ESRB, 2016\)](#) has argued that a delay in the energy transition could affect systemic risk via three main channels, including more frequent natural catastrophes. The [Network for Greening the Financial System \(NGFS, 2019\)](#) has emphasized that climate change could have much larger impacts than other structural changes affecting the financial system. [Bolton et al. \(2020\)](#) suggest that climate change could even be the cause of the next systemic financial crisis. Others seem less convinced. Fed Governor [Waller \(2023\)](#) has argued that climate change is not a serious risk to the U.S. financial system, for instance because climate physical risks are not likely to have a large effect on economic growth. [Hansen \(2022\)](#) focuses on climate analyses by central banks and issues a warning that there can be reputational costs to overselling insights from long-horizon climate stress tests. In a similar vein, [Cochrane \(2021\)](#) argues that climate change is highly unlikely to have a drastic and abrupt effect on financial institutions in the short term.

We see this study's forward-looking perspective as a main contribution to the literature on climate-related financial vulnerabilities, which will be reviewed in more detail in Section 2. At present, there are only few examples of scenario-based studies regarding flood events ([Bellia et al., 2025](#); [Johnston et al., 2023](#); [Lepore and Mok, 2024](#)). Compared to these three papers, our analysis uses a wider range of flood scenarios, has more detailed data on real estate exposures, or presents more detailed results on implications for lenders' capital positions. We make calculations for flood scenarios that are severe and unlikely from today's perspective, as is common in financial stress testing. We first focus on 32 scenarios for floods due to a single breach in flood defence systems. The single-breach flood scenarios we consider have a probability varying roughly between once in every 100 and once in every 10,000 years. Next, we consider even less likely events by studying six extreme multiple-breach scenarios. In the end, all 38 flood scenarios we study have low probabilities of materializing, which is reflective of the high level of flood protection in the Netherlands. By focusing on such unlikely — and, sometimes, very extreme scenarios — we aim to understand how tail events surrounding climate physical risk could have financial stability implications. This forward-looking approach also sets our paper apart from related work studying how actual natural disasters have impacted the financial system ([Blickle et al., 2022](#); [Gramlich et al., 2023](#); [Koetter et al., 2020](#); [Klomp, 2014](#)).

In terms of data, we use various sources that have detailed information on real estate exposures. As the global financial crisis of

2007–09 has shown, real estate is an asset class with strong implications for financial stability. Real estate is also relevant from the perspective of climate physical risk, as floods can potentially lead to major damages to homes and commercial properties. We use detailed loan data per end-2020 for around 3 million residential properties and 175,000 commercial properties that underlie close to EUR 650 billion in exposures secured by real estate. In this way, we can study implications of uninsured flood-related property damages for lenders' credit risk.³

In terms of analysis, we trace the possible impact of floods on bank capital via a number of steps. First, we use information on location-specific inundation depths under the 38 individual flood scenarios to compute property damages for each of the roughly 3 million properties in our data set. Second, we translate these property-specific damages into increases of the loan-to-value ratio of individual bank loans. In principle, we are able to analyze such LTV increases at the level of scenarios, banks, and types of exposure (i.e., either commercial or residential real estate loans). However, we will always present financial impacts that are aggregated across the banks in the sample. Third, using the shocks to LTV ratios, we compute implications for key credit risk parameters at the level of individual loans. Here, we consider changes in the probability of default (PD), the loss given default (LGD), and the risk weights of individual loans. Lastly, we consider the impact on bank capital, which we measure via the changes CET1 ratio. In the empirical section, we will discuss these financial impacts from the perspective of 38 individual flood scenarios and two main types of real estate exposures (residential and commercial).

Turning to results, we estimate that flood-related property damages could cause a drop in system-wide bank capital that mostly ranges between 30 and 50 basis points. We show that flood-related capital depletions are a function of flood-related vulnerabilities and financial vulnerabilities. Concerning financial vulnerabilities, we highlight the role of the starting-point loan-to-value (LTV) ratio of the loan for which the damaged property serves as collateral. We show that the flood impact increases when properties are damaged that serve as collateral for loans with relatively high LTV ratios. Relative to current levels of bank capital, one could argue that the estimated levels of depletion seem manageable—especially since we already consider tail-risk events. At the same time, it is important to note that our analysis focuses on only one transmission channel and is subject to a number of assumptions. In particular, if climate change continues, more frequent floods or flood-related macrofinancial disruptions may have larger implications for financial stability than this paper's estimates indicate. An extension in Section 8 sketches how quickly capital depletions would increase, once growth declines are assumed also to affect borrowers' probability of default.

2. Related literature

This section discusses two strands of related literature. First, papers that study how climate change could affect financial stability. Second, research estimating by how much flood events so far have led to property damages.

Starting with work on the link between climate change and the financial system, floods have not received much explicit attention yet ([Acharya et al., 2023](#)). In contrast, much of the focus has been on how disorderly transition paths could affect financial stability. [Battiston et al. \(2017\)](#) consider exposures of 50 European banks to climate policy relevant sectors. Using data on over EUR 1 trillion of equity holdings, they find that while direct equity exposures of these banks to fossil fuels are small, the overall exposures to climate policy relevant sectors are large as well as heterogeneous. Similarly, [Vermeulen et al. \(2021\)](#) find that financial losses under disruptive transition paths could be sizeable,

³ One logical extension would be to account for flood damages to other types of land use, for instance agriculture.

suggesting that climate-transition shocks warrant close attention from a financial stability perspective. Jung et al. (2021) propose a new measure (CRISK) which is the expected capital shortfall of a financial institution in a climate stress scenario. This measure indicates a strong rise in climate vulnerabilities for banks in the U.S., U.K., Japan and France in recent years.

One particular distinguishing aspect of our paper is its forward-looking approach to flood risk. At present, there are only few examples of scenario-based studies regarding flood events. Using a set of flood scenarios for the Netherlands, Lepore and Mok (2024) find that climate change amplifies the adverse impact on banks' capital, but that stronger flood defenses in the Netherlands can help mitigate some impacts. As a complement to the approach in our paper, they focus on macro-financial aspects, such as destruction of physical capital and productivity shocks, rather than granular exposures of banks to real estate. Focusing on Canada, Johnston et al. (2023) find that the direct damages of flooding have modest impacts on loss given default for Canadian financial institutions. In contrast to our paper, implications for capital positions of financial institutions are not sketched. Bellia et al. (2025) use a simulation model to study how river flooding could affect German regional banks. They find that bank losses could increase by 1 percentage point of total assets under a scenario with a 3-degree increase in global warming. In contrast to our paper, their data is not geocoded, but consists of aggregate data on assets and capital per bank.

Other examples of a forward-looking approach are climate stress tests by various central banks and prudential authorities. Flood risk has been one element of recent exercises by, for instance, the ACPR/Banque de France (2025), the ECB (2022), and the Federal Reserve (2024). Our paper contributes by providing a deep dive into this specific peril. Ideally, the insights of our study can inform future climate stress tests by such institutions.

Its forward-looking approach also sets our paper apart from related work that has studied how actual natural disasters have impacted the financial system. For instance, Blicke et al. (2022) consider data from the last 25 years and find that natural disasters have had insignificant or small effects on U.S. banks' performance. Taking a cross-country approach, Gramlich et al. (2023) also find little evidence that natural disasters have affected banks' Tier 1 capital ratio so far. Klomp (2014) focuses on large-scale natural disasters between 1997 and 2010 and finds that these disasters do increase the likelihood of bank defaults. Studying banks' lending decisions, Koetter et al. (2020) focus on a major flood of the river Elbe in Germany and find evidence for recovery lending (as opposed to less lending).

A second relevant stream of literature considers how actual floods have led to property damage. For floods along the Meuse river in the Netherlands in the mid-1990s, Daniel et al. (2009) estimate a price decrease of up to 9%. Atreya and Ferreira (2015) combine a hedonic pricing model with geospatial information to study the 1994 flood in Albany, Georgia, and find damages up to 48%. Pistrika and Jonkman (2010) assess a database of 95,000 damage estimates for buildings in New Orleans after hurricane Katrina and report an average damage of 43.3%. Damage rates of more than 50% are reported for roughly a quarter of the assessed properties. Two further studies focus on floods in the United Kingdom. Using a repeat-sales model, Beltrán et al. (2019) estimate price declines in flooded areas between 21% (in case of coastal flooding) and 25% (in case of inland flooding). These price declines are estimated to be short-lived, as differences are no longer significant after a period of 5 years. Garbarino and Guin (2021) focus on one severe flood event in England in 2013–14. They find relatively small price effects related to this flood. Compared to unaffected properties in the same district, properties in affected areas shows decreases in sales prices of, at most, 4.2%.⁴

⁴ There is also related work studying whether flood risk is already incorporated in property prices. For instance, Hino and Burke (2021) find little evidence that housing markets fully price information about flood risk in aggregate. See also Beltrán et al. (2018), Bosker et al. (2019), Mol et al. (2020), or Mutlu et al. (2023).

In principle, one could take some of these estimates from the literature to calibrate property damages. However, there is a better alternative in the form of a rich scenario set constructed by Dutch flood experts. As discussed in the next section, this scenario set has detailed information on probabilities and inundation depths for more than 5000 flood scenarios. This scenario set gives us the best available estimate for the probability and impact of flood events in the Dutch context from today's perspective.

3. Data

This paper uses information from three data sources: data on loans secured by real estate, administrative microdata from the property registry, and supervisory data on capital adequacy. The first two sources allow us to estimate the flood damages per property and map these into the credit risk parameters of the loans that these properties secure. A key point is that we use loan data to compute multipliers for credit risk parameters. Also, we use microdata for information on property characteristics that are needed to compute flood-related property damages. Lastly, we use supervisory data to obtain starting points for capital ratios and credit risk parameters. Our analysis uses data for eight banks. The banks in this sample all have a substantial exposure to Dutch real estate. Considering also the concentrated nature of the Dutch banking system, this means the analysis covers nearly all of the outstanding loans secured by real estate at the time. In turn, these exposures related to real estate represent close to 40% of total bank assets in the Netherlands at the time.⁵

First, the loan data covers residential and commercial properties that served as collateral for bank loans held on the balance sheet.⁶ The data on exposures contains detailed information, such as the counterparty, the contract, the instrument and the protection related to each real estate loan. We use information for bank loans as per end-2020.⁷ Table 1 shows descriptive statistics for the loan data. In the sample considered, the collateralization of the outstanding loans (as indicated by the average loan-to-value ratio) was around 50%. For new loans, the average LTV ratio at origination was around 77% for residential properties and 66% for commercial real estate. A substantial amount of the outstanding debt for residential properties was non-amortizing: 51% of the loans was interest-only. Only a small share of loans was in default (0.9% for residential, and 3.6% for commercial real estate).

Fig. 1 illustrates the distribution of real estate exposures across municipalities in the Netherlands. The largest exposures are in the western half of the country, as this is where the main cities such as Amsterdam (the darkest blue element in Fig. 1), Rotterdam, and the Hague are located. The western half of the Netherlands is also the part of the country that is partly below sea level.

Second, we rely on administrative microdata at the level of the property available from Statistics Netherlands (in Dutch: CBS). This data set covers all objects registered in the basic property registry. This registry contains several types of information collected for administrative purposes. To begin with, the registry has information on the tax value of each property. In addition, the data set contains a range of property characteristics, such as floor surface (in square meters), location (at the postal-code level) and the type of real estate. We use postal codes to determine how much a property would be inundated under different flood scenarios, while we use the other characteristics

⁵ For confidentiality reasons, the individual data sources have not been combined.

⁶ Hence, the data set has no information on securitized and fully-amortized instruments. As discussed in Vroombout (2025), the share of mortgages that is being securitized has, in fact, been declining for some years now.

⁷ This vintage of the data was also a basis for Caloia and Jansen (2021). Presumably, the inherent vulnerability of real estate exposures to flood risk will not have changed materially since end-2020, although ideally one would like to use updated information at some point.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics.

Loan characteristics (%)	Residential properties		Commercial real estate	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median
Interest rate	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.3
LTV	52.3	54.5	53.4	49.0
LTV-O New business	76.7	83.0	66.0	65.0
LTV-O Starters, New business	86.6	95.0	–	–
Interest-only	50.9	50.7	22.4	0.00
Outst.amount (*1000 €)	183	153	1677	358
Protection value (*1000 €)	384	321	4914	606
	Residential properties		Commercial real estate	
Type of property (in %)	Detached	32.8	Residential	52.7
	Apartment	14.3	Offices	26.9
	Terraced	42.4	Retail	7.0
	Commercial	2.3	Industrial	4.9
Location (in %)	Large 4 cities (%)	14.3	Large 4 cities (%)	24.1
Portfolio characteristics (N, unless indicated)	Instruments	6,129,774	Instruments	46,744
	Protections	5,352,319	Protections	222,928
	o/w properties	3,030,383	o/w properties	175,721
	Contracts	3,124,998	Contracts	40,979
	Exposure (€mn)	577,217	Exposure (€mn)	70,730
	In default (%)	0.90	In default (%)	3.62

Note: Summary statistics for loan data related to residential and commercial properties that serve as collateral for a sample of Dutch banks at end-2020. The top panel presents information on loan characteristics, such as the loan-to-value (LTV) ratio and the LTV ratio at origination (LTV-O). The labels *Starters* and *New business* refer to first-time buyers in the housing market and to newly originated loans, respectively. The numbers in the top panel are percentages, unless indicated otherwise. The bottom panel presents information on the type of property (in percentages of total), the location of the property (percentage share in largest 4 cities), and portfolio characteristics, including the number of properties that serve as collateral for the loans.

in the computations for the flood-related damages to properties in case of a flood.

Third, we use supervisory data for individual banks from the Common (COREP) and Financial (FINREP) Reporting frameworks. The COREP and FINREP formats cover various aspects of banks' balance sheets, profitability, capital adequacy, and asset quality. The analysis in this paper uses starting points for credit risk parameters and capital positions from FINREP/COREP, also for positions per end-2020.

4. Methodology: Flood scenarios and damage calculations

4.1. Selection of flood scenarios

We study scenarios with floods in those parts of the Netherlands that are protected by primary flood defence systems.⁸ There are two reasons. First, the concentration of economic activity and real estate is the highest in those areas. A flood event occurring there would be more likely to have macrofinancial implications.⁹ Second, flood-related property damages are uninsurable in those cases. In principle, the government could decide to provide financial compensation after a flood. However, such support would be discretionary and it might well take some time to become available. In the immediate aftermath of a flood event, presumably, banks would then need to account for higher credit risk.

First, we consider 32 scenarios with single-breach flood events. These are scenarios with one local failure in flood protection. We take these 32 scenarios from an open-source information system called the LIWO.¹⁰ In total, the LIWO contains more than 5000 flood scenarios

⁸ In the Dutch context, these would be designated 'type B' floods. See also Section 1 of the appendix for details on flood types.

⁹ Flood events in unprotected areas are more likely to occur than the scenarios considered in this study. However, given the scarcity of real estate in such unprotected at-risk areas, credit risk impacts are comparatively small. See also Caloia and Jansen (2021) and Lepore and Mok (2024).

¹⁰ LIWO is an acronym for Landelijk Informatiepunt Water en Overstromingen (Nationwide Information source Water and Floods). See also <https://basisinformatie-overstromingen.nl/>. URL last accessed on 25 May 2024.

for the Netherlands. We use two selection criteria. First, we want to cover all relevant parts of the Netherlands that could be vulnerable to breaches in primary flood defence systems. As indicated in Fig. 2, this means the 32 scenarios cover various parts of the country, including regions close to the sea as well as those close to the main rivers.¹¹ Second, per area of the Netherlands, we then always select the scenario for which available calculations (as found in the LIWO) indicate the highest expected damages. Here, we use a minimum threshold of EUR 500mn. in terms of expected property damages. Based on these two criteria, we select 32 scenarios that are among the most impactful ones in terms of potential property damages.

Second, we consider even more severe circumstances by studying the financial implications of six extreme multiple-breach scenarios. Here, we use scenarios constructed by Dutch flood experts (Ten Brinke et al., 2010). Each of these six multiple-breach scenarios is composed of dozens of larger and smaller dike breaches occurring at the same time. We emphasize that these are circumstances that the flood experts, at the time, considered to be at the edge of what could happen in a highly unlikely situation. Fig. 3 shows the extent of the floods under these six extreme multiple-breach scenarios.

4.2. Inundation depths per postal-code area

For each flood scenario, a key metric is the inundation depth per location. Here, we have to take into account data granularity. The LIWO allows the user to assess inundation depth at the level of up to a 100 × 100 m grid. However, the data on bank loans can only be used at the level of four-digit postal codes. In practice, this could be either a small town or a neighborhood in a larger city. While that level of detail is still a major improvement compared to the nationwide supervisory data available in FINREP, it does mean we need to make assumptions when calculating the flood impact per scenario.

¹¹ During the summer floods of 2021, a part of the southern Dutch province of Limburg was also heavily affected. Given our focus on damages due to breaches of primary flood defence systems, we cannot include scenarios for this region, however. For a damage assessment, see Kok et al. (2023).

Fig. 1. Distribution of real estate exposures.

Note: This figure shows the distribution of EUR 650bn. in Dutch banks' real estate exposures by municipality at end-2020. Darker colors indicate a higher level of exposure. This figure combines information for exposures to residential and commercial real estate.

To obtain a proxy for the representative water depth per postal-code area, we proceed as follows. First, we select the part of the postal-code that contains residential or commercial properties. We need to do so, as the inundation map also overlaps with other types of land use, such as agriculture or infrastructure. Given our focus on real estate, we exclude these other types of land use from our calculations. Next, we calculate the mean water depth over the built-up area only. The not-inundated parts of the built-up area per postal code are included as zero values when taking the mean level for inundation depths. This means that the mean water level is representative for all properties in the postal code area, including those properties that are not affected by the flood.

4.3. Computing property damages

Our method for calculating property damage broadly follows the SSM method. The SSM is the standard approach for calculating flood damage in The Netherlands (Slager and Wagenaar, 2017). This SSM method makes a distinction between direct damages (i.e. to the property) and indirect damages (i.e. to household goods and personal effects). We focus on the former, as it is only the direct damages to the property that would affect the collateral value.

The SSM method has two key inputs for determining property damages. First, a maximum amount of damage per property, for instance specified as a euro amount per m^2 for residential properties. Second, a damage factor $\theta(h)$ that increases non-linearly with inundation depth h , the so-called damage function. Slager and Wagenaar (2017) provide separate damage functions for different types of properties, such

as single-family homes and apartments (for residential properties) or offices and industrial properties (for commercial properties). We can apply almost all of these specific damage functions directly using the information in the loan data. The exception concerns apartments, which constitute 14% of the properties in the data set (see Table 1). For apartments, the damage factors (i.e. $\theta(h)$) differ between floor levels. However, information on floor levels is not available in our data set. Therefore, we use a weighted average of the damage functions for ground-floor and first-floor apartments. We place most weight (65%) on the damage function for first-floor apartments, given that we neither want to overestimate nor underestimate damages. Section 3.1 of the appendix provides further details. There are a few additional differences between this study and the most recent SSM-damage calculations (Slager and Wagenaar, 2017). Our study uses more recent exposure data (2020 instead of 2014), only includes properties that serve as collateral for a loan (instead of all properties), and uses a mean water depth per postal code (instead of per 100×100 m grid cell). Despite these differences, we find a strong correlation ($\rho = 0.95$) between our damage estimates and those from the SSM method. Section 3.2 of the appendix provides further details.

The key parameter linking floods to financial risk is ϕ . With this parameter ϕ , we denote the flood-induced decline in the collateral value of the property p . We compute this parameter at the property-level for each flood scenario. As described in the next section, this parameter ϕ will then affect the loan-to-value for each loan i for which the property serves as collateral. To compute ϕ , we first calculate the

Fig. 2. Scenario set for single-breach floods.

Note: This figure gives an overview of 32 scenarios with single-breach floods. In each scenario, a local breach in the system of flood defence leads to a flood in a specific part of the country. The source for the flood scenarios is the LIWO, which is an open-source information system. From the LIWO, we select the scenarios that have the largest impact in each compartment of the flood protection system. In addition, we use a cut-off value of EUR 500mn. for overall estimated damages.

property-specific damages (in euros, price level 2020) as:

$$damage_p^S = \theta(h)_t^S \cdot max\ damage_t \cdot A_p \cdot \pi \tag{1}$$

Here, S indexes the scenario, p the property, t the type of property, while h denotes inundation depth (in meters). The parameter θ is the damage factor. This factor, which lies between 0 and 1, denotes the fraction of maximum damages that are incurred. The parameter θ is specific to property type and inundation depth. Furthermore, $max\ damage$ is the maximum flood damages (per property type, in 2011 prices) as provided by Slager and Wagenaar (2017). The information on the size of the property (A , in m^2) is obtained from the administrative microdata available from Statistics Netherlands. The last term (π) is a correction factor to compute damages in terms of the 2020 price level, which is necessary as the collateral values are all observed at end-2020. The appendix discusses in detail how we calibrate this parameter π .

Lastly, we obtain ϕ by expressing the damages as a fraction of the observed collateral value in the loan data, where we restrict the value of ϕ to be in the $[0,1]$ interval.

$$\phi_p^S = \min\left(\frac{damage_p^S}{property\ value_p}; 1\right) \tag{2}$$

5. Methodology: Credit risk and capital depletion

The credit risk impact for banks will be driven by a few key parameters. We discuss, in turn, our models for the loss-given-default and the probability-of-default parameters. We close by linking the credit risk impact to banks' capital adequacy, which we measure by the CET1 ratio. We measure the credit risk impact over a one-year horizon. The starting points are taken as per end-2020. Our approach closely follows the Basel regulatory approach to credit risk, in particular for IRB (internal ratings based) exposures for which real estate serves as collateral.

5.1. Loss given default

The loss given default (LGD) indicates the part of the loan that the lender cannot recover in case the borrower was to default. Based on the loan data, we model LGD paths as a function of flood-related collateral damages. To compute such LGD paths, two other metrics are important: the loan-to-value ratio and the loss-given-loss.

First and foremost, the estimated decline in the collateral value (ϕ_p^S from Eq. (2)) will increase the loan-to-value ratio of the loans for which the property serves as collateral. This means those loans will become

Fig. 3. Scenario set for extreme multiple-breach floods.

Note: This figure gives an overview of six scenarios for multiple-breach floods. Dutch flood experts constructed these six extreme multiple-breach scenarios in 2007. These six scenarios are intended to represent extreme impacts that are still theoretically conceivable, yet very unlikely.

riskier from the perspective of the lender. The LTV of loan i under flood scenario S is given by:

$$LTV_i^S = LTV_i^0 \cdot \frac{1}{1 - \phi_p^S} \quad (3)$$

Here, p indexes properties, LTV_i^0 represents the starting-point loan-to-value ratio (per end-2020), and LTV_i^S is the LTV ratio for loan i per flood scenario. The parameter ϕ_p^S is computed based on Eqs. (1) and (2) above. One important assumption behind Eq. (3) is that LTV ratios are regularly monitored and updated. This assumption is in line with Article 208 of the Capital Requirement Regulation (CRR). This article requires institutions to monitor the value of the property on a frequent basis—at least once every year for commercial properties and once every three years for residential properties. This article also requires institutions to review the valuation when the value may have declined materially relative to general market prices, which would match well with a situation where a flood affects properties in a specific part of the country. A second assumption is that the property damage represents a good proxy of the decline in the value of the property that would be determined by an appraiser. We would argue that the damage method discussed above provides the currently best-available estimates of the actual property damages in the event of a flood.

Next, the increase in the LTV ratio under the flood scenario will increase the loss-given-loss (LGL) of the loan. The LGL indicates whether a lender will be able to cover its exposures when selling the property that serves as collateral. A positive LGL indicates that the lender will not be able to recover the exposure in full. The link between the LTV and LGL is given by:

$$LGL_i = \frac{\max[0; \text{exposure} - \text{liquidation value}]}{\text{exposure}} \quad (4)$$

Here, the liquidation value is a prudent estimate of the price of the asset in the event of a forced sale. If we divide both the numerator and the denominator by the property value and then condition on the flood scenario S , we obtain the following expression:

$$LGL_i^S = \max \left[0; \left(\frac{LTV_i^S - \text{sales ratio}_p^S}{LTV_i^S} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

Here, the sales ratio denotes the ratio between the liquidation and current value of the property. Our calculations for the liquidation value take into account the costs for getting the property in a condition ready for sale. So, the sales ratio in each flood scenario S is reduced by an amount equal to the property damage.¹²

Third, an increase in the LGL will increase the LGD parameter of loan i . This relationship is given by:

$$LGD_i^S = ((1 - \text{probability of cure}) * LGL_i^S) + \text{costs} \quad (6)$$

Here, LGD indicates the loss-given-default for loan i per flood scenario S , while the LGL is the loss-given-loss as computed above. The *probability of cure* denotes the frequency of loans that were previously classified as defaults and are now classified as performing. The last term (*costs*) indicates the administration costs that the bank would incur when moving ahead with selling the property.

For each of the single-breach flood scenarios, we make calculations for LGD paths based on Eqs. (1)–(6). Given the details of the loan data, we do so separately for residential and commercial properties. The starting-point data is a cross-section of exposures backed by real estate at end-2020. When available (i.e. for commercial properties), we use the reported information on liquidation values (for sales ratios) and administration costs. For residential real estate, this information is not available to us. Therefore, we use values in line with those reported for commercial real estate exposures.

Turning to system-wide impacts, the scenario-specific LGD multiplier for banks (relatively to the starting point) is given by:

$$m_{LGD}^S = \sum_b \sum_i w_b w_i \frac{LGD_{i,b}^S}{LGD_{i,b}^0} \quad (7)$$

Here, the weights w_b and w_i represent the bank-level and loan-level exposures, as a share of the total system exposure and the total bank exposure, respectively. For a given flood scenario S , the final impact

¹² In other words, we calculate as follows $\text{sales ratio}_p^S = \text{sales ratio}_p^0 * (1 - \phi_p^S)$.

on the banks reflects their relative exposure to the flood scenarios, the associated property damages, as well as their starting point for the LGD.¹³

5.2. Probability of default

A second key parameter for credit risk is the probability of default (PD). At first sight, the PD may seem less relevant to this paper, given our focus on how property damages map into loss-given-default parameters. However, empirically PDs are found to comove with loan-to-value ratios. Therefore, we also estimate the probability that a borrower defaults on the loan, conditional on each of the single-breach flood scenarios, using a panel data approach that includes LTV ratios as one of the explanatory variables. We estimate the following equation:

$$y_{i,b,t} = c_b + \beta' \mathbf{Z}_{i,b,t} + \delta' \mathbf{X}_{i,b,t} + u_{i,b,t} \quad (8)$$

Here, the dependent variable $y_{i,b,t}$ is the default status of the counterparty i of bank b at time t . The set of control variables $\mathbf{X}_{i,b,t}$ includes the mortgage type (amortizing, deferred-amortization, or interest-only), the interest rate type (variable, fixed, or fixed with reset), the residual maturity, the LTV at inception, the type of real estate that serves as collateral, and whether or not a National Mortgage Guarantee (NHG) is attached to residential loans.¹⁴ We estimate a pooled OLS model using the loan data.¹⁵ The main independent variables $\mathbf{Z}_{i,b,t}$ are the current loan-to-value, as well as the mortgage interest rate and regional GDP growth. The parameters β then capture the effect on the default probability of collateral, funding and income risk, respectively. We obtain the system-wide PD multiplier in each scenario as:

$$m_{PD}^S = \sum_b \sum_i w_b w_i \frac{E(y_{i,b,t} | \mathbf{X}_{i,b,t}, \mathbf{Z}_{i,b,t}^S, t = T, s = S)}{E(y_{i,b,t} | \mathbf{X}_{i,b,t}, \mathbf{Z}_{i,b,t}, t = T)} \quad (9)$$

Here, the numerator represents the predicted value of Eq. (3) conditional on the values of the LTV under each scenario, as of the last reporting period. The weights w_b and w_i are again the bank-level and loan-level exposure shares.

In principle, we could extend the analysis further by also projecting PD paths in line with the implied change for each main independent variable $\mathbf{Z}_{i,b,t}$ under the various flood scenarios. In particular, we could include considerations such as growth slowdowns or increases in risk premia. For the baseline estimates, we will focus solely on the role of property damages. The baseline effect on the PD that we show, therefore, comes purely from the flood-related damages and their effect on the LTV ratio via ϕ_p^S . An extension in Section 8 will sketch how quickly capital depletions would increase, once growth declines are assumed also to affect borrowers' probability of default.

5.3. The impact on the CET1 ratio

We measure the impact of flood damages by computing how changes in credit risk parameters affect system-wide bank capital. The metric we use is the CET1 ratio, i.e. the ratio between banks' high-quality regulatory capital (CET1 capital) and their risk weighted assets

¹³ Under the Basel framework, banks would be encouraged to consider downturn LGDs. For the present paper, we do not follow this route. First, this approach is typically not suited for long-term structural risks such as climate change, for which historical realizations may underestimate current and short-term risks. This is why this paper proposes a scenario-based analysis. Second, downturn LGDs reflect downturn economic conditions but do not incorporate adverse climate conditions. This is due to the absence of systemic climate events in the data.

¹⁴ The availability of such an NHG guarantee serves as a key risk mitigant, as the bank would be more likely to recoup a sizeable part of its outstanding exposure in case of a default.

¹⁵ We estimate the model at annual frequency. The sample is 2012–2018 (residential properties) or 2015–2020 (commercial properties).

(RWA). Our calculations take as a starting point a system-wide CET1 ratio of 16.7%, i.e. the weighted average across the banks in the sample at the end of 2020.

First, we consider the flood-related changes in expected loss (EL) for banks, which will affect the numerator of the CET1 ratio. Expected loss can be computed by multiplying the probability of default (PD), the loss given default (LGD), and the exposure at default (EAD, measured in euros). Hence, the expected loss for bank b on loan portfolio i under flood scenario S is then given by the product of starting-point risk parameters (PD, LGD, EAD, as given by the supervisory data) and multipliers (m , as computed by us):

$$EL_{b,i}^S = PD_{b,i} \cdot LGD_{b,i} (m_{PD}^S m_{LGD}^S) \cdot EAD_{b,i} \quad (10)$$

As expected loss increases under the flood scenarios, banks are assumed to book additional provisions, thus lowering the available CET1 capital to hold against their risk weighted exposures. Although we compute changes in EL at the level of individual banks — as well as portfolios and flood scenarios — we will only report system-wide impacts.

Turning to the denominator of the CET1 ratio, we compute risk weighted assets as per the requirements from the Basel Framework. We use the risk weight functions prescribed under the internal rating based (IRB) approach, i.e. we compute risk weighted assets as the product of exposures at default, a constant factor of 12.5% (which represents the inverse of the 8% Basel minimum capital requirement) and a factor K . This factor K is the relevant capital requirement from the Basel Framework that depends, among others, on the scenario-specific paths for LGDs and PDs that we compute. For each scenario, the increase in K relative to the starting point is driven by the increase in the PD and LGD parameters of performing exposures and the increase in the LGD for defaulted exposures.¹⁶ Having computed scenario-specific RWAs, we can then also derive the implied multipliers for risk weights (m_{RW}^S) by comparing them to the starting-point RWAs (as given in the supervisory data):

$$\begin{aligned} m_{RW}^S &= \sum_b \sum_i w_b w_i \frac{(RWA)_{i,b}^S}{(RWA)_{i,b}} \\ &= \sum_b \sum_i w_b w_i \frac{K_{i,b}^S}{K_{i,b}} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Having derived bank-specific, portfolio-specific, and scenario-specific paths for expected loss and risk weights, we can then consider implications for capital positions. As noted above, we only report system-wide impacts. Comparing the paths for EL and RWAs to the starting points (as given by the supervisory data), we can compute changes in the CET1 ratio per flood scenario as:

$$\Delta CET1 \text{ ratio}^S = \frac{CET1}{(RWA)} - \frac{CET1 - \Delta EL^S}{(RWA) + \Delta(RWA)^S} \quad (12)$$

Here, ΔEL^S represents the difference between the EL under the flood scenario and starting-point expected loss, while ΔRWA^S denotes the scenario-specific change in the risk weighted assets. Both the increase in the expected loss and the higher risk weights will lead to a lower CET1 ratio under the flood scenario. Hence, we will often use the term capital depletions when discussing changes in the CET1 ratio.

6. Results

This section discusses how flood-related property damages would affect the capital position of the Dutch banking system. To start with, we show the relationship between our calculated property damages and capital depletion. Fig. 4 illustrates this relationship. The figure

¹⁶ See also Section 31 of https://www.bis.org/basel_framework/index.htm?m=2697. A last detail is that the RWA formula for residential and commercial real estate exposures differs for the full maturity adjustment and the asset correlation parameter, which we take into account in the calculations.

Fig. 4. Property damage and capital depletion under 38 flood scenarios.

Note: This figure presents a scatter plot for estimated property damages (in EUR bn., horizontal axis) and banks' capital depletion (in basis points, vertical axis). The blue diamonds show results for 32 single-breach flood scenarios; the red circles indicate results for six extreme multiple-breach scenarios. The property damages (horizontal axis) are the sum total of direct damages to residential properties and commercial real estate that serve as collateral for bank loans. Insurance policies would not cover these property damages. We use the CET1 ratio to measure bank capital. The capital depletion is a weighted average across a sample of Dutch banks. The dashed gray line plots an estimated fractional polynomial of degree 2.

shows estimated property damages (in EUR bn., horizontal axis) and the system-wide decline in the CET1 ratio (in basis points, vertical axis). Here, the horizontal axis shows combined damages for residential and commercial real estate. The gray line plots an estimated fractional polynomial of degree 2. The figure shows results for the single-breach scenarios (blue diamonds) as well as the multiple-breach floods (red circles).

The figure indicates that the 32 single-breach flood scenarios would all have similar implications for bank capital. Three of the multiple-breach scenarios have comparable implications for CET1 capital as well. Overall, this cluster of 35 scenarios would be characterized by property damages between EUR 0.5bn and EUR 3bn. (in price level of 2020). Capital depletions are estimated to be between 30 and 50 basis points. There is an indication that capital depletions would taper off quickly as property damages move toward zero, which is an indication of non-linearity. Turning to the other end of the spectrum, the remaining three scenarios — all of them multiple-breach cases — stand out in terms of total damages and capital depletion. For the two scenarios with property damages around EUR 6 bn., we estimate a CET1 decline of around 75 basis points. For the most extreme scenario, we estimate a capital depletion due to property damages of close to 110 basis points. This scenario considers the unlikely case in which a major multiple-breach event leads to a flooding of most of the western part of the Netherlands.

In terms of composition, we find that most of the capital depletion is due to an increase in the risk weights. The top panel of Fig. 5 provides a breakdown across scenarios between the two key components of the change in the CET1 ratio (as per Eq. (12)). For the single-breach scenarios, the average contribution of expected losses to capital depletion is around 6 basis points, i.e. around 15% of the total depletion. The average contribution of risk weighted assets is, in turn, 34 basis point. When moving to the multiple-breach scenarios, the RWA effect is even more prominent. On average, the contribution to the overall depletion is 66 basis points. Another decomposition (Fig. 5, bottom

panel) indicates that the role of PDs already strongly increases when considering multiple-breach scenarios. Across the 38 adverse scenarios, most of the capital depletion is due to increase in LGDs. However, the contribution of the PD becomes pronounced for multiple-breach scenarios. It should be noted again that this increase in PDs is purely due to damage-related increases in loan-to-value ratios. Adding further macrofinancial shocks, such as growth declines, will further amplify the capital impact through higher PDs.

The key linking pin underlying such aggregate results is Eq. (3), which connects flood-related damages (the ϕ parameter) to loan-to-value ratios. To explore this mechanism, we use outcomes for one of the 38 flood scenarios as an illustration. Fig. 6 shows these results, which are for one of the multiple-breach scenarios. The horizontal axis indicates the average property damage in that area (i.e. the mean value for ϕ in Eq. (3)), while the vertical axis indicates the average starting point of the loan-to-value ratio (i.e. LTV_i^0 in Eq. (3)). Each red circle corresponds to a postal code area that is affected under this scenario. The size of the circle indicates how many properties within that area would be affected by a flood. Of these four metrics, the LTV ratio is a key indication of financial vulnerabilities, while the other three indicate how vulnerable the property itself would be to floods. In this multiple-breach scenario, many postal codes areas are affected. Within those areas, the number of damaged properties is high, while average damages can run up to 70%. Importantly, we find that large expected damages and high financial vulnerabilities overlap in this case. The upward slope of the solid line with fitted values suggests that, on average, the larger damages occur in areas which are characterized by higher starting-point LTV ratios. To some extent, it is this combination of flood-related and financial vulnerabilities that contributes to the overall large impact of this extreme multiple-breach scenario.

Lastly, to provide some further intuition, we sketch implications of heterogeneity across banks. Here, we ran additional analyses to study the correlation between bank characteristics and estimated capital depletions across three dimensions. When doing so, we find that estimated

Fig. 5. Decomposing the capital depletion.

Note: This figure shows a decomposition for capital depletions across the 32 single-breach and the 6 multiple-breach scenarios. In the top panel, the contributions to the overall depletion are split between expected losses and risk weights, as per Eq. (12) in the main text. The bottom panel shows a decomposition across credit risk parameters, i.e. the probability of default (PD) and the loss given default (LGD).

depletions are significantly and positively correlated to the share of properties located in flood zones ($\rho = 0.19$) and the share of real estate to total assets ($\rho = 0.59$). Estimated depletions are lower when banks are more exposed to apartments ($\rho = -0.39$), as these are more often located at higher floors and, therefore, less likely to be damaged.

7. Discussion

Taken at face value, our estimates for tail-risk events would suggest that the Dutch banking system is resilient in the face of flood risk. We find that the system-wide capital depletion under adverse flood scenarios would be mostly between 30 and 50 basis points. Relative to recent levels of bank capital, such depletions seem manageable. In this section, we provide some further intuition for this finding. At the same time, we highlight how various elements of our research design are relevant for the interpretation of our findings.

Starting with flood-related vulnerabilities, although a sizeable portion of the Netherlands is below sea level, our findings reflect the fact

that the level of flood protection is high. Considering the occurrence of a flood — let alone a multiple-breach event — already implies that one is imagining situations with low levels of probability of ever occurring. More importantly, given the set-up of its flood protection mechanisms, a local flood in one part of the Netherlands would not automatically also affect the rest of the country. This level of containment makes it unlikely that a large share of banks’ real estate exposures would be damaged at the same point in time. Fig. 7 provides an illustration of this point. The figure focuses on residential properties (the appendix has a comparable figure for exposures to commercial real estate). In the figure, the horizontal axis shows (as a fraction) how many of the properties are damaged in the various scenarios. The vertical axis shows the average value loss (as a fraction of current value) of damaged properties. Hence, the values on the vertical axis correspond to the parameter ϕ defined above. In nearly all of the flood scenarios we consider, more than 95% of the residential properties would not incur damages. The main exception is the multiple-breach scenario for the

Fig. 6. Financial vulnerabilities and property damages.

Note: This figure illustrates financial vulnerabilities (vertical axis) and flood-related property damages (horizontal axis) for one multiple-breach scenario. Each red circle corresponds to an area that is affected under this scenario. The size of the circle indicates the number of properties affected by the flood. The horizontal axis indicates the average property damage (i.e., ϕ in Eq. (3) of the main text). The vertical axis indicates the average starting point of the loan-to-value ratio (i.e., LTV_i^0 in Eq. (3)).

western part of the Netherlands. This particularly extreme multiple-breach flood would affect close to 25% of the residential properties that serve as loan collateral.

Turning to assumptions, our paper has abstracted from various other types of socioeconomic impacts that a flood may have. Even though property damages will be a relevant component of the overall effect on bank capital, there are other ways in which floods could wreak havoc. For instance, if a major flood were to lead to a decline in economic growth, the increased probability-of-default would lead to a further increase in banks' credit losses (Caloia and Jansen, 2021; FSB, 2025). Also, if climate change were to continue, more frequent floods could mean that banks have less time available to restore their capital position. An extension in Section 8 will sketch how quickly capital depletions would increase, once growth declines are assumed also to affect borrowers' probability of default. We leave a further exploration of such macrofinancial channels for future research.

A second important assumption concerns our treatment of the LGL estimate, in particular the sales ratio. In our calculations, the sales ratio is reduced by an amount equivalent to the estimated property damage under each flood scenario. However, this approach does not account for the fact that in densely-populated affected areas, the sales ratio is likely to decline more substantially due to broader market effects, such as reduced demand, buyer uncertainty, and potential neighborhood-wide depreciation. Given that it is not immediately clear how to calibrate such broader market effects, we leave this point for future research.

A third important assumption concerns the damage calculations that we use. Taking these damage curves as given, the potential property damage will be maximized at a certain level. For instance, a single home of 100 m² would have a worst-case estimate damage of EUR 120,000. In light of property values at the time, it is then not surprising that we find that the ϕ parameter is rarely close to 1. Even for multiple-breach scenarios, this happens in less than 1% of the cases. Even though we use the most current damage curves available in the Dutch

context, there is quite some debate on whether these curves may be on the conservative side. For instance, Endendijk et al. (2023) compare actual damages in the wake of the 2021 summer floods to the numbers suggested by the method of Slager and Wagenaar (2017). They find indications that actual damages may have been higher than suggested by the SSM-method for inundation depths below 175 cm. Any upward revision of damages curves would have direct implications for our credit risk calculations, naturally.

A final assumption concerns the static nature of our analysis. We do not account for any mechanisms through which lenders could respond to increasing flood risk. Going forward, adapting to climate change could be an important way to mitigate potential financial stability impacts of flood events (IMF, 2024). Strengthening flood protection will play a key role in minimizing the likelihood of a flood event as well as the potential damages. Adaptation could also take the form of decisions related to the built environment, i.e., where and how to build. But, prudent lending decisions could also be a way of adapting to potential impacts of physical climate shocks.

8. Extension with PD dynamics

There are various ways in which to extend the analysis. Such extensions are relevant, given that our baseline estimates in Fig. 3 focus on one specific transmission channel and are subject to various assumptions. To give an idea of potential implications, this section considers an additional shock to economic growth. We apply this additional shock only in the case of the most extreme multiple-breach scenario, given that this is the case where macroeconomic adversity would be most likely to occur.

So far, the literature reports mild and short-lived growth declines in the wakes of natural disasters (Raddatz, 2007; Strobl, 2011; Cavallo et al., 2013; Von Peter et al., 2024). We use estimates by Von Peter

Fig. 7. Damaged properties and value losses across flood scenarios.

Note: This figure shows scatter plots for the fraction of damaged properties (horizontal axis) and associated property damages (as fraction of value, vertical axis). The blue diamonds show results for 32 single-breach flood scenarios; the red circles indicate results for six extreme multiple-breach scenarios. The average property damages correspond to the mean of the parameter ϕ in Eq. (2) of the main text. This parameter ϕ indicates the percentage value loss for affected properties in a given flood scenario. The results shown are for residential properties—the appendix has an equivalent figure for exposures to commercial real estate.

et al. (2024), who find that major disasters reduce growth by 1 to 2 percentage points on impact.

Feeding both the lower (1 p.p.) and upper (2 p.p.) estimate for growth declines from Von Peter et al. (2024) into our PD calculations, we estimate that system-wide capital depletions would be between 157 and 306 basis points. Compared to our baseline estimates, which account for property damages alone, this means an additional effect through a PD channel of between 50 and 200 basis points. Further work could consider a wider set of additional amplification and feedback channels, for instance building on the FSB (2025) conceptual framework for climate-related vulnerabilities.

9. Conclusions

Using 38 tail-risk scenarios, we study how flood-related property damages for which no insurance coverage is available would affect credit risk for a sample of Dutch banks. Focusing on the Netherlands is useful to understand possible implications for financial stability, given that the country has both a large banking sector and an inherent vulnerability to floods. We calculate implications for bank capital using data on EUR 650 billion in exposures backed by real estate. Across the 38 scenarios, we find that the system-wide capital depletion would mostly range between 30 and 50 basis points. In terms of transmission channels, we show that the financial impact is a combination of flood-related vulnerabilities (such as the proximity of the property to the country's main rivers) and financial vulnerabilities (such as the starting-point loan-to-value ratio of the loan for which the damaged property serves as collateral).

What do our findings imply for the on-going debate on climate change and financial stability (cf. Carney, 2015; Waller, 2023)? Admittedly, compared to current levels of bank capital, a flood-related capital depletion of 50 basis points or less would seem manageable. Still, there are some nuances that should be emphasized. First of all, flood protection matters. Our low estimates for capital depletion reflect, to a large extent, the high levels of investment that the Netherlands has

been making in an adequate system of flood defence. It would be interesting to conduct a similar study for other jurisdictions, in particular for those where flood protection may perhaps be less strong. Second, it is important to note that our estimations focus on one particular channel (namely, uninsurable property damages) and are subject to a number of assumptions (for instance, concerning damage curves), suggesting effects of flood events may well turn out to be larger. Third, looking ahead, banks' capital depletion may well increase if climate change continues. More frequent floods and associated macroeconomic disruptions may then have stronger implications for financial stability than these present-day estimates on increased credit risk indicate. For instance, if floods were to happen more often, banks would have less time available to replenish capital. In addition, if floods were to lead to recessions, banks would face a further increase of credit losses, as sketched by the extension in Section 8 of this paper. Another effect could be that a flood event makes this type of climate-related risk more salient,¹⁷ which could lead to a sudden revaluation of properties located in flood zones.

We hope the methodological approach of our paper provides a useful basis for the further study of financial stability implications of climate physical shocks, both in the Netherlands and in jurisdictions where climate protection gaps may be widening in the years to come. Understanding such implications in a timely fashion is important, not only because of increased credit risk after a flood event, but also in light of feedback effects to households and non-financial companies if the stability of the banking system would be significantly impaired.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Francesco G. Caloia: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kees C.H. van**

¹⁷ Based on two surveys of Dutch homeowners, Jansen (2024) finds that flood risk awareness has indeed increased since the 2021 summer floods.

Ginkel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **David-Jan Jansen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfs.2026.101545>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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